

OBSERVATIONS ON LOCAL STRAIN FIELDS IN CFRP STIFFENED ELEMENT TESTS USING DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION

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SUMMARY

The local skin/stiffener strain state during failure initiation and propagation in stiffened elements was characterised using digital image correlation, fractography and FEA. Detailed mapping of the strain fields during loading was obtained and a link between failure initiation in bending element tests and full-scale panels was established.

Keywords: *Stiffened Panels, Element Tests, Digital Image Correlation, Fractography*

INTRODUCTION

The use of carbon-fibre polymer composites in stringer-stiffened structural components is primarily limited by skin/stiffener detachment induced during postbuckling. To date, the preferred route to characterise and optimize buckling performance has been through manufacture and test of full-scale structural panels, but this is expensive and time consuming, and does not provide designers with the freedom to explore new and novel structural configurations, thus inhibiting the development of improved designs.

An alternative approach is to use smaller stiffener element tests, and a number of such methods have been developed at NASA [1] and NLR [2]. Such elements offer the opportunity for designers to explore different configurations using minimal resources. A key requirement of such element tests is that they truly mimic the stress states in full-scale panels, such that the results from elements can be used to optimize full-scale structures. However, it has yet to be demonstrated that the failure processes which develop in elements represent those observed in real structures.

Current research [3] has focused on delamination as the initiation process in skin/stiffener debonding. The work here has demonstrated that ply splitting is a key mechanism that dictates the performance and failure of skin/stiffened structures.

The aim of the work reported here was to characterise the local skin/stiffener strain state in elements prior to, and during the development of failure. This was part of a larger study investigating element configurations that could provide enhanced skin/stiffener performance, and thus offer superior post-buckling performance over existing structures [4]. For clarity, the work reported here focuses on just two skin/stiffener configurations but demonstrates the methodology followed by the research. The approach has been to pursue experimental studies using Digital Image Correlation (DIC) to provide

qualitative details of the local strain conditions at the skin/stiffener interface at the initiation of failure. These observations have been employed in conjunction with finite element analysis to extract the local strain conditions in the elements, the findings of which were validated against fractographic observations from the tests. Finally, for one configuration, a full scale panel test was conducted, in which the local strain conditions adjacent to the stiffeners were characterized using DIC, and compared to the observations from the relevant element tests.

SPECIMEN CONFIGURATIONS

In this study, elements have been reported on two configurations; a benchmark and an advanced configuration (configuration D) utilising a modified stacking sequence. The benchmark configuration was then also tested as a full-scale stiffened panel.

The benchmark was based on the EDAVCOS SFN5 [5] panel, which had been investigated in a previous study on post-buckled stiffened panel behaviour. A similar material system (AS4/8552 and FM300-K adhesive) and geometry was used with an identical stacking sequence. The skin had a stacking sequence of $[+45^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_{3s}$ and the stiffener was $[+45^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ_3/90^\circ/0^\circ_3/-45^\circ/+45^\circ]$. This design was chosen because the benchmark configuration had been observed to undergo unstable skin/stiffener debonding at failure.

The design philosophy for configuration D was to study the effect of:

1. A softer/more compliant skin through changing the layup whilst keeping the number of plies (and consequently geometry) constant.
2. Creating a potentially more tortuous path for crack propagation from the skin/stiffener interface into the skin.

The skin laminate of this configuration had a compliant layup $[{+45^\circ/-45^\circ}]_3/0^\circ_2/90^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ]_s$, with a longitudinal flexural modulus (homogenised) almost half that of the benchmark. The outer surfaces consisted solely of angled ply lamina to study the effect this could have on failure propagation. Due to the higher compliance, it was expected that for a given applied load, a larger degree of deformation would occur thus inducing higher strains compared to those in the benchmark. Hence it was anticipated initiation would take place earlier. However, the stacking sequence was chosen to promote stable failure progression.

All specimens were secondarily bonded, i.e. the skin and stiffener were cured separately prior to being subjected to bonding to form the final stiffened element. Prior to testing, the surfaces were suitably speckled with spray paint to facilitate the use of DIC to monitor the strain fields.

TESTING DETAILS

The element specimens dimensions are shown in Figure 1, and these were tested under three loading conditions; three and four point bending and lateral tension (Figure 2) [1, 2]. At least five elements were tested for each loading configuration. All tests were conducted in a screw driven universal Instron 4505 test machine under displacement control, with a loading rate of 2mm/min. One pair of cameras for DIC image acquisition

monitored the specimen sides at the tip of the stiffener. Tests were taken to final failure, defined when the crack front had reached the mid-span of the specimen.

Figure 1: Element dimensions (width is 20mm for both the benchmark and configuration D)

Figure 2: Element test conditions

Full Scale Stiffened Panel Test

The nominal panel dimensions of the full-scale benchmark panel are presented in Figure 3. A compression test to failure was carried out and monitored using DIC, shadow Moiré and strain gauges. This was done in an in-house, custom built worm wheel driven compression test machine with a loading capacity of 2.5MN, under displacement control loading in the 0° direction (i.e. parallel to the stiffeners). Two pairs of cameras for DIC image acquisition were set up to monitor the stiffener face of the panel; one pair captured the full panel (two stiffener bays and the three stiffener caps), designated as camera pair A, whilst another pair captured a smaller region which included the full width of the bay and part of the central stiffener flange, designated as camera pair B (Figure 3a).

The panel was first loaded up to an applied strain of $-1200\mu\epsilon$ to verify the applied loading was uniform (i.e. all gauge readings were within 10% of the average applied strain). The panel was then loaded to final failure at a loading rate of 0.5mm/min, with DIC images recorded at a constant rate of once every two seconds. Buckling was deemed to have occurred when strain gauges in the bays exhibited more than 10% divergence.

Figure 3: Nominal panel and stiffener dimensions, showing the local region monitored using DIC (see Figure 7).

TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Element Tests

The results reported here focus on the DIC results, with the strain fields just prior to failure initiation presented.

Benchmark

The full field strain results generally exhibited similar global behaviour between nominally identical specimens. Results for the lateral tension tests were of a higher resolution because this loading configuration was much more conducive to DIC measurement, since the test rig did not obscure the field of view. Consequently, in the lateral tension tests, the resolution was such that layered strain distributions could be distinguished (Figure 4d).

Attempts were made to extract quantitative data for the strain conditions at initiation but the amount of scatter in these localised results were high, and much greater than the scatter in the global results (such as applied strain at initiation). As a result, only qualitative comparisons could be made using the DIC results for the elements.

Under all three loading conditions, a highly positive peel strain was anticipated at the stiffener tip, but this was not always observed; data at this discontinuity could not always be accurately calculated and was automatically disregarded by the software. This resulted in gaps in the calculated strain field images.

Figure 4: DIC out-of-plane peel strain (ϵ_{zz}) for the benchmark element at initiation

Widthwise strains (ϵ_{xx}) were also measured; DIC was able to resolve anticlastic and Poisson's ratio effects, i.e. expansion in the top surface in bending and contraction in the overall specimen in tension. A high degree of width-wise contraction was seen at the stiffener tip in the skin/stiffener interface (adhesive) region in all tests. Just ahead of this contraction was a relatively long zone of expansion, especially prominent in the higher resolution lateral tension results, but also in the bending tests.

Configuration D

From the DIC results (Figure 5), it was apparent that configuration D exhibited larger strains (peel, width-wise and shear) at initiation compared to the benchmark. DIC results also picked out an area of high strain concentration about a quarter of the way through the thickness.

Figure 5: DIC strain results at initiation in three point bending for the benchmark and configuration D elements

It was noted that the lateral tension tests failed prematurely due to delamination initiating at the end grips, which grew longitudinally towards the mid-span at the same skin ply interface that the DIC results had indicated sites of strain concentration.

From fractographic analysis, element failure was found to be associated with ply split development adjacent to the skin/stiffener interface [4]. This implied that the critical strains for element failure were the local intralaminar peel and shear strains ϵ_{22} and γ_{12} respectively. Although the DIC results could not provide quantitative measurements, FEM models of the elements were developed, in which the observed loading at failure in the experiments was imposed. These results were compared to those from the original EDAVCOS SFN5 panels and similarities in terms of failure mechanisms, locations and initiation strains were seen. This provided the basis for a methodology with which the local strains at failure in the elements could be deduced [4].

Stiffened Panel Test

The DIC studies on the stiffened panel were very successful; the development of the mode shape obtained is presented in Figure 6. Buckling occurred at an applied strain of $-2485\mu\epsilon$ as three half waves developed in each bay. The out-of-plane displacements (δ_z) from the DIC results were also extracted along the centre of a bay, which showed that a maximum δ_z (5.89mm) was located in the middle antinode of one of the bays (i.e. the panel mid-span). There was little variation in δ_z between the corresponding antinodes of the two bays, implying the applied loading was uniform. Final failure occurred at an applied strain $-5768\mu\epsilon$ as stiffener debonding, followed by compression failure of the stiffeners and skin. However, subsequent fractographic analysis showed that the adhesive between the skin and stiffeners was defective, which had led to premature debonding of the stiffeners. This explained why this panel had not performed as well as an identical panel configuration reported elsewhere [6].

Figure 6: DIC results showing out-of-plane displacements (δ_z) for the benchmark.

The local strain field in one of the bays near the stiffener tip (Figure 3a) was captured using DIC and the strains in the local material orientation ($+45^\circ$) are shown in Figure 7. These indicated that the highest strain concentrations were around the stiffener tip.

Figure 7: DIC local strain field results, with respect to the surface ply, from the benchmark (see Figure 3a). N.B. Stiffener edge is on the left hand side.

Comparison between experimental and predicted results

Details of the FE models used in this section can be found elsewhere [4]. Full scale panel buckling was predicted to occur at an applied strain of $-2600\mu\epsilon$ in the form of three half waves in each bay; this was slightly higher than the experimentally observed applied strain of $-2485\mu\epsilon$. However, the predicted δ_z along the midbays were almost identical to those measured using DIC (Figure 8), suggesting the model was reliable.

Figure 8: Comparison between DIC and FEM for δ_z along the midbays at an applied strain of $-5768\mu\epsilon$

A comparison between the DIC and FEM are shown as contour plots of the critical intralaminar peel (ϵ_{22}) and shear (γ_{12}) strains just prior to failure in Figures 9 and 10 respectively. There was good agreement on the intralaminar peel strain (Figure 9) but, for the intralaminar shear strain (Figure 10), there were some areas where the DIC had observed higher shear strains than had been predicted near the central stiffener tip.

a: DIC data overlaid onto panel image

b: FE output for the surface ply

Figure 9: Intralaminar peel (ϵ_{22}) strain field in the surface ply ($+45^\circ$) at $-5768\mu\epsilon$ (failure) on the benchmark panel

a: DIC data overlaid onto panel image

b: FE output for the surface ply

Figure 10: Intralaminar shear (γ_{12}) strain field in the surface ply ($+45^\circ$) at $-5768\mu\epsilon$ (failure) on the benchmark panel

Since failure was observed to have initiated at the ply interface, the panel test results were studied in light of the local critical strains in the elements. Figure 11 shows the measured intralaminar peel and shear strains 2mm from the stiffener tip and compares them to the corresponding prediction; these were in good agreement.

Previous studies [4] have shown a link between failure initiation in the form of ply cracking for element tests and stiffened panels. The proposed failure methodology entailed using the intralaminar strains from the bending tests at failure initiation to predict failure initiation in the stiffened panel; when both the critical ϵ_{22} and γ_{12} given by the bending tests are exceeded in the surface ply of stiffened panel, failure initiation was deemed to have occurred via ply splitting. The full scale panel tests were intended to validate this hypothesis. Figure 11 also shows the critical intralaminar strains from the corresponding four point bending element tests; this suggests that the local strains in the surface ply had not reached those required to initiate ply split development, and thus panel failure. These results support the fractographic observation that the adhesive was defective, and led to premature failure in this panel before ply splitting could develop.

Ply splitting had been observed to have been the critical fracture process in the EDAVCOS SFN5 panel [6, 7]. It was seen during this study that the failure mechanisms that occurred in the element tests coincided with the observed failure conditions in the full-scale panel. This suggests that ply splitting can be a critical damage mode in the skin/stiffener debonding process, and that element tests which exhibit this mechanism can be used to predict full-scale panel behaviour. However, further studies are required to fully demonstrate that such a methodology is robust enough for post-buckling design on composite components.

Figure 11: Surface ply (+45°) intralaminar peel (ϵ_{22}) and shear (γ_{12}) strains 2mm from stiffener tip at $-5768\mu\epsilon$ (failure) on full scale benchmark panel, with the corresponding 4 point element failure conditions also shown.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Although DIC was limited for quantitative measurement of the local strains from the element tests, it did provide an effective technique for qualitative analysis of the strain fields at the skin/stiffener interface. This was particularly apparent in the results from configuration D, where a strain concentration corresponded to the observed delamination failure plane.

The high scatter observed in the local DIC results was attributed to local geometry changes, material inhomogeneity, as well as the effect of noise from the measuring system. However, these local perturbations did not significantly reflect in global results and the overall failure mode of the specimens.

DIC was successfully used to characterise both the global strain conditions over the stiffened panel and the local strain field around the stiffener tip and the quantitative results compared very well to predicted ones. This suggests that DIC could provide a powerful tool for characterising strain conditions in composites structures prior to and during damage development and failure.

In the work reported here the surface strains near the stiffener tip were characterised in both elements and full-scale panel. A proposed methodology has been developed, using

a combination of experimental element tests and FEM predictions, which enables the detailed strain field at the site of damage initiation at skin/stiffener interfaces to be deduced. This methodology provides a link between element and full-scale structural behaviour, although further work is required to demonstrate that this methodology is robust enough to use for engineering design of post-buckled structures. However, if successful, this methodology will facilitate the use of element tests to optimise future post-buckled designs.

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